

Carbone and Visual Structure Indicators in Soil Health Assessment After No-Till Adoption Under Agro-Pedological Context in Algeria

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Abstract

Soil health indicators are a set of measurable and interpretable chemical, physical and biological parameters related to soil functional processes that can be used to assess the state of soil health under different agroecosystems. Multiple indicators are examined in the case of soil health assessment after adoption no-till system such as, total carbon and its fractions, nitrogen, bulk density, aggregate stability and infiltration of water. In this chapter, we use organic carbon (particulate, associated and microbial) and visual structure indicators to assess soil health after a short and long duration of adoption no-till by depth under agro-pedo-climate context in Algeria.

Three plots submitted in NT to different transition durations (3, 6 and 9 years) and a control plot submitted in CT were studied. Soil samples were taken at two depths (H1: 0-10 and H2: 10-20 cm). Analytical results showed that indicators in the surface horizon were significantly ($p < 0.05$) improved by increasing the NT transition duration, especially during the longest transition durations. The particulate organic carbon is the most sensitive soil indicator of the gradual no-till transition. The multiple correlation study showed that the evolution of the selected soil indicators is similar between the transition durations (3, 6 and 9 years) in H1. Or, in H2, the evolution of these indicators is similar only between the 6 and 9 year transition durations.

Keywords: Structure visual, Aggregate stability, Bulk density, Microbial organic carbone, Particular organic carbon, No tillage.

Introduction

Soil is an ecosystem incorporated minerals, organic matter, organisms, water and air. It maintains a gradual flow of matter and energy in the environment with various physical, chemical and biological functions (Hatfield et al., 2017). The degradation leads not only to a decrease in agricultural productivity of the soil but also to the deterioration of water, air and as well human health (Bünemann et al., 2018). Tillage, for example to incorporate crop residues and fragment the soil which promotes rapid mineralization of organic carbon, soil destruction, affects agricultural productivity and causes soil erosion (Kassam et al., 2019; Boizard et al., 2017). The no-till system is considered an alternative to the tillage system, in which crop residues are left on the surface of the soil which improves the storage of organic carbon, the structure and thus prevents soil erosion (Kassam et al., 2019).

The transition from conventional to no-till can bring gradual changes in soil indicators before reaching a new equilibrium (Boizard et al., 2017; Vian et al., 2009). The metadata analyzes have shown the importance of several indicators for the assessment of soil health in space and time when cropping systems change. These indicators must be accessible and sensitive to changes in soil management and interpretable for management decisions (Guo, 2021; Bünemann et al., 2018, Triantafyllidis et al., 2018). Total organic carbon has been described as the most cited indicator in the assessment of soil health (Triantafyllidis et al., 2018). Thus, its organic fractions, in particular the particulate and microbial fraction, are generally more sensitive to soil disturbances (Qi et al., 2021; Plaza-Bonilla et al., 2013) due to their contributions to the improvement of functions, such as soil structuring, storage of organic matter and provision of habitat for microorganisms in the soil (Guo, 2021; Bongiorno et al., 2019). Soil structure is a key to soil biological, chemical and physical quality. The spatial arrangement of aggregates and porosity is a main aspect of soil structure (Hatfield et al., 2017). Soil structure is one of the indicators of soil directly affected by change in total and active organic carbon (Rabot et al., 2018). This indicator has been indirectly evaluated using physical properties such as aggregate stability and bulk density (Blanco-Canqui et al., 2018; Boizard et al., 2017). Currently, soil structure is considered an important indicator in the evaluation of soil health. It can be accessed directly in situ by visual methods (Celik et al., 2020; Ball et al., 2017).

However, the introduction of new indicators such as: organic carbon fractions and visual soil structure in soil health assessment after adoption of short and long term no-till system under agro-pedo-climate condition in Algeria.

Materials and Methods

Characteristics of site and experimentation

The study was conducted in 2017 in the province of Sétif (36°09'N, 5°21'E) in Algeria. This region is characterized by a semi-arid climate type with an annual rainfall of 380 mm and mean temperature of 13.7°C (Kribaa et al., 2001).

An experiment is made up of four plots which correspond to the transition duration from no-till for the cultivation of wheat. These plots were selected on the basis of homogeneity on slope and soil texture. These plots are characterized by a silty-clay texture soil and a slight slope (<2%). The control phase (CT) corresponding to the plot maintained in conventional tillage. It consists of seedling the wheat a turning over the surface horizon of the soil using a plow at a depth of 25 cm. The plots (NT3), (NT6) and (NT9) correspond to the no-till transition duration (3, 6 and 9 years)

respectively. They consist in seedling the wheat directly (no tillage) on the residues of the previous harvest. All plots were subjected to fertilization at a dose of 150 kg/ha with ammonium phosphate (12% N, 52% P and 0% K) at a dose of 100 kg/ha with urea (46% N). Plots no tillage were weeded before seeding using glyphosate 2.5 liter/ha.

Soil sampling and analysis

Soil samples of number 03, disturbed or undisturbed, were collected from two soil depth (0- 10 cm and 10-20 cm). Total organic carbon (TOC) was analyzed according to Walkley method described by Nelson et al., (1996). Particulate organic carbon (POC) was measured following Cambardellal et al., (1992) method. The associated organic carbon (OAC) was calculated by subtracting POC from TOC. The microbial biomass carbon (MBC) was estimated using fumigation-extraction method. All these parameters were analyzed on disturbed soil samples.

Visual structure (VS), aggregate stability (AS), soil bulk density (BD) were determined on from undisturbed soil samples. The (SS) was evaluated by visual observations and using scoring method of Ball et al., (2017), which rates VS from good structure quality (score 1) to bad structure quality (score 5). The (AS) was determined according to Bissonnais et al.,(1996) method and (BD) was estimated using a cylinder (100 cm³).

Statistical analysis

The experimental results were subjected to statistical analyzes with the Rcmdr (R 4.02) platform. Data were subjected to analysis of variance and correlation test between soil indicators at $p < 0.05$. To better understand the degree of this variability a principal component analysis was also performed.

Results and Discussion

Organic carbon indicators

Table 1 show that the organic carbon indicators present significant differentiation between treatments in the two soil depths ($p < 0.05$).

At 0-10 cm depth, the NT9 can significantly increase the organic carbon (TOC, POC and MBC) with 42, 71 and 68%, respectively and lose 15% of the (AOC) carbon but not significant, compared to the CT. At this depth, the (TOC) in (NT9, NT6 and NT3) consists mainly of (POC) with (70% of the total carbon). Or, in CT, the (TOC) consists of 40% (POC). The longer the transition duration greater the accumulation of crop residues. The increase of organic matter in the NT with crop residue mulch treatments near the soil surface was probably caused by decomposition of applied mulch and less mineralization of in situ organic matter due to the absence of tillage (Kassam et al., 2019).

At 10-20 cm depth, NT9 increases the carbon concentration of (TOC, POC, AOC and MBC) with (32, 59, 3 and 44%), or, NT3 decreased the carbon with (22, 44, 5 and 18%), respectively, compared to CT. At this depth, the change in organic carbon indicators was best presented by the adoption duration of 9 years and similarly by the duration of 6 years. However, the NT3 do not allow an improvement of the organic matter because of their short duration of adaptation. These results are similar to several works, particularly in semi-arid Mediterranean conditions and in soil texture (Celikl et al., 2020; Jemail et al., 2021).

Table 1. Total organic carbon (TOC), particular organic carbon (POC), associated organic carbon (AOC) and microbial biomass carbon (MBC) at depth 0-10 and 10-20 cm under after no tillage adoption.

Treatments	TOC (g kg ⁻¹ soil)	POC (g kg ⁻¹ soil)	AOC (g kg ⁻¹ soil)	MBC (g kg ⁻¹ soil)
0-10 cm				
NT9	17.5 ^c	11.7 ^c	5.8 ^{ab}	0.31 ^d
NT6	15.9 ^b	10.5 ^b	5.4 ^a	0.24 ^c
NT3	15.2 ^b	09.8 ^b	5.4 ^a	0.22 ^b
CT	10.2 ^a	03.4 ^a	6.8 ^b	0.10 ^a
10-20 cm				
NT9	12.8 ^c	05.8 ^c	7 ^a	0.16 ^d
NT6	12.1 ^{bc}	05.4 ^{bc}	6.7 ^a	0.14 ^c
NT3	08.7 ^a	02.4 ^a	6.3 ^a	0.09 ^a
CT	11.1 ^b	04.3 ^b	6.8 ^a	0.11 ^b

CT- conventional tillage; NT3- 3 years, NT6- 6 years; NT9- 9 years.. Different lowercase letters within a column indicate significant differences between treatments ($P < 0.05$).

Structure indicators

Table 2 presented a change in soil structure visual (VS), aggregate stability (AS) and bulk density (BD) between no-till transitions duration as a function of soil depth.

Table 2. Soil structure (SS), bulk density (BD) and aggregate stability (AS) at depth 0-10 and 10-20 cm after no tillage adoption.

Treatments	VS (score)	BD (g cm ⁻³)	AS (mm)
0-10 cm			
NT9	1 ^a	1.41 ^a	1.86 ^d
NT6	1 ^a	1.42 ^b	1.66 ^c
NT3	1 ^a	1.43 ^c	1.51 ^b
CT	3 ^b	1.58 ^d	1.14 ^a
10-20 cm			
NT9	1.3 ^a	1.48 ^a	1.55 ^d
NT6	2 ^c	1.52 ^c	1.45 ^c
NT3	4 ^d	1.65 ^d	0.94 ^a
CT	1.6 ^b	1.50 ^b	1.21 ^b

CT-conventional tillage; NT3- 3 years; NT6- 6 years; NT9- 9 years. Different lowercase letters within a column indicate significant differences between treatments ($P < 0.05$).

At depth (0-10 cm), the (NT9, NT6 and NT3) can improve the indicators (VS and BD) by (67 and 11%), respectively, compared to CT. The longest duration NT9 can increase the size of the aggregates up to 39%, or the shortest duration (NT3) has a 25% increase in aggregates, compared to CT.

At depth (10-20 cm), only the (NT9 and NT6) which allow improvement (SS, BD and AS), but less important than in the surface horizon. Or, the (NT3) causes a degradation of the structure indicators (VS, BD and AS) with (100, 10 and 22%), respectively, compared to CT. This means that the short duration of no-till adoption (3 years) does not improve the structure indicators (Celik et al., 2020; Jemai et al., 2013).

Contribution of organic carbon indicators to the improvement of soil structure

A very good correlation ($-0.81 < r < 0.94$) between the organic carbon indicators (TOC, POC and MBC) and the structure (VS, AS and BD) over all the soil depths (tableau Table 3).

Table 3. Correlation matrix between fractions of organic carbone (TOC, POC, AOC and MBC) and structural quality (SS, BD and AS).

	AOC	AS	BD	MBC	POC	VS	TOC
AOC	1	-0.47	0.57	-0.72*	-0.78*	0.41	-0.69
AS		1	-0.89*	0.92**	0.91**	-0.87*	0.95**
BD			1	-0.86*	-0.91**	0.96***	-0.93**
MBC				1	0.97***	-0.75*	0.97***
POC					1	-0.81*	0.99***
VS						1	-0.86*
TOC							1

**correlation is significant at $p < 0.01$, *correlation is significant at $p < 0.05$.

Several authors (Horn et al., 2019; Abdallah et al., 2021; Qi et al., 2021) show that increasing organic matter content can increase carbon sequestration in macroaggregates. This is a very important energy source for microorganisms and can contribute to the aggregation of soil and therefore provides good structural organization. Or, the carbon (AOC) shows no significant correlation with structure indicators (VS, BD and AS). According to several researchers (Celik et al., 2020; Jemai et al., 2013), this indicator is linked to clay and silt particles in the soil ($< 53 \mu\text{m}$) and can contribute to the chemical stability of organic matter more than the physical stability in soils fine texture.

Figures 1 and 2 explains a better variability with 96 % on the factorial axis (Dim1) followed by the variability with (10.5%) on the axis (Dim 2) and cumulative variability with 85.7 %.

The analyze in Figure 1 show that all the soil indicators are well projected on (Dim1) and well correlated on the correlation circle. The soil indicators AS, POC, TOC and MBC are located positively, while AOC, VS and BD are located negatively on (Dim1). Corresponding from Figure 1 to Figure 2, there is an association between NT transition durations by depth and soil indicators.

According to the degree of similarity, the change of the soil indicators makes it possible to group the effect transition durations no tillage by depths into three clusters that are in descending order (H1NT9 - H1NT6 - H1NT3) , (H2NT9 - H2NT6 - H2CT) and (H2NT3 - H1CT). In this study, NT adoption for 9 and 6 years led to an improvement in structure and carbone indicators at (H1) than at (H2). This change is limited to depth (H1) by the adoption duration of 03 years.

Fig. 1. Principal component analysis of soil indicators (VS, BD, AS, TOC, POC, AOC and MBC).

Fig. 2. Principal component analysis. of factors individuals (H1CT, H2CT, H1NT3, H2NT3, H1NT6, H2NT6, H1NT9 and H2NT9).

All the soil indicators studied can contribute significantly to the differentiation between homogeneous groups of similarity (transition time per depth), but the indicators most sensitive to the transition from CT to NT system are POC, TOC, MBC, BD, AS with $-0.95 < r < 0.99$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.0001$ (Table 4).

Table 4. Correlation (r) between the cluster variable and the soil indicators at $p < 0.05$.

	POC	TOC	MBC	BD	AS	VS	AOC
Correlation	0.99	0.99	0.96	-0.95	0.94	-0.88	-0.70
P-value	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	0.003	0.04

This indicator presents labile organic matter which can contribute to the storage of organic matter, to biological activity, to the improvement of structural quality (Bongiorno et al., 2019).

Conclusion

Under Algerian agro-pedo-climatic conditions, no-tillage (NT) can improve soil quality compared to conventional tillage (CT). The CT system at the base of the plow favors organic matter and structure at H2 depth than at H1.

By comparison, the adoption of NT can significantly increase the indicators organic carbon. This increase may contribute to improved organic matter storage, biological activity, bulk density, aggregate stability and structural morphology. The longer the duration of adoption (>6 years), the more the improvement on soil quality can generalize to the depth of the soil and therefore can improve the agricultural productivity of soil and protect it against erosion.

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